

INTERNAL CONTROL OF RISK MANAGEMENT IN NEW PRODUCT ACTIVITIES

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Abstract

Establish a “culture” of risk management in the firm. A risk management culture emphasizes the importance of risk management in the firm at all levels, as part of the daily activities of each member of the firm. The goal of creating a risk management culture is to create a situation in which partners and firm personnel instinctively seek out risks and evaluate their impact in making effective operational decisions. The inherent nature of risk management is that it is not geographically dependent or specific to any country or location. The principles for establishing this culture are universal and relevant to any geographic location. The sections in this module cover the components of establishing a risk management culture. This module examines ethical issues and their impact on your firm’s exposure to risk. It examines the process of dealing with a client, as well as how to best manage your risk in this area.

Keywords: Risk, management, business, organizational structure, National Bank, Standard, products, processes, transactions.

Introduction

Internal control over risk management:

The scope of the internal control system related to risk management should include, at a minimum:

- a) the compliance of the internal control system with the level of risks inherent in the bank's business activities;
- b) the establishment of authorities and responsibilities for monitoring the compliance of policies, procedures and limits;
- c) the establishment of accountabilities and a clear distribution of functions between the established and controlling structures;
- d) an organizational structure that clearly reflects the business activities;
- e) the adequacy of procedures to ensure compliance with laws and regulations;
- f) effective, independent and objective review of the procedures for evaluating the bank's operations;
- g) adequate examination and review of the management information system;
- h) complete and adequate documentation of the bank's management scope, organizational procedures, audit results and responses based on audit results;
- i) examination of the regulation of the bank's activities and bank management actions, identification of material weaknesses and their review.

The risk management review should include at least the following:

- a) at least once a year, a regular review of risk management by risk management or relevant authorized persons, as well as appropriate assessments by the compliance officer of the risk management organizational structural unit and auditors of the internal audit department;
- b) the review and assessment may be intensified and its scope expanded in accordance with the risk faced by the bank, market changes and risk assessment management methods;
- c) the review should also be carried out by an external auditor or other qualified party who has a good understanding of risk management technologies;
- d) the following issues should be particularly taken into account when assessing and reviewing risks:

- Methods, assumptions and changes used to assess risks and set risk limits;
- Comparison between the results obtained from simulations or forecasting and the actual results;
- Comparison between the assumptions used in the model and the actual situation;
- Comparison between the limits set and the actual risks;
- Determination of the appropriateness of the risk assessment and risk limits in relation to past performance and current positions.

Risk management for new products and activities:

The bank should develop written policies and procedures for the risks inherent in new products and activities.

The risk management policy procedures for new products and activities should establish at least the following:

- a) Standard operating procedures and authority for managing product and activity risks;
- b) Identification of all risks specific to new products and activities;
- c) A trial period for the assessment and monitoring methods specific to new products and activities in order to ensure testing of the methods from the perspective of prudential and other aspects of banking activities;
- d) An information system for accounting for new products and activities, which will reflect at least the risk profile and the level of profit and loss of the product and activity;
- e) A legal analysis of the new product and activity, taking into account the possibilities of possible legal risks; Analysis of the compliance of new products and activities with the prevailing law and normative acts.

If the bank is a representative of a business group, especially a financial group that has a centralized risk management process, the bank should ensure that the risk assessment process is consolidated as accurately as possible, as the consolidated monitoring and evaluation process should set clear limits that are met at all levels of consolidation.

In the case of transactions between structural units and branches, in which a certain risk position arises, the bank should:

- a) clearly identify internal transactions;
- b) reconcile internal transactions in the accounting process, which should aim to reflect the results of the consolidated financial statements;
- c) ensure that the risk positions arising from internal transactions are assessed, monitored and controlled by the risk management structure;
- d) ensure that consistent limits are set.

The bank should regularly, at least monthly, compare changes that arise from differences in accounting standards applied between the profit and loss statement and internal transactions and promptly review and correct these differences.

In case of transactions between entities within a business group, the bank should also ensure that the transactions are carried out correctly so that the accounts of the business group are accurately reflected in the financial statements.

Supervisory role in the verification of the bank's risk management processes:

When implementing the supervisory policy, the National Bank will pay special attention to the adequacy of risk management in the bank, so that these systems allow for the timely identification, adequate assessment, effective monitoring and control of prudent management and use of risks.

The use of risk management will accelerate the assessment of possible losses of the bank from the point of view of banking supervision, which may have a negative impact on the bank's capital. In view of this, they are required to assess risks on a quarterly basis and submit a report on the risk profile to the National Bank of Georgia together with the financial statements.

This report should include a comparison with the previous quarter. It should also reflect all relevant risk levels and dynamics, in accordance with the complexity of the bank's business activities. The report on the risk profile submitted to the National Bank should be identical to the report submitted to the Directorate and the Management Committee on this issue.

The bank is also required to submit reports on all new products and activities no later than 7 (seven) days after their implementation.

The bank should be required to submit other reports to the National Bank in the event that the bank's situation may result in significant financial losses, or for other reasons that the National Bank considers significant. In this regard, such a bank's situation may be considered as follows:

- a) the National Bank provides intensive or special supervision to the bank;
- b) the bank faces significant market and liquidity risk;
- c) the external (market) situation is subject to severe fluctuations and is not subject to the bank's control.

The frequency and forms of reporting provided for in this Article shall be determined on the basis of consultations between the bank and the National Bank, as they are based on the current situation of the bank and the risks that may be faced by the bank at a given stage.

In the process of the NBS system or thematic examination of banks, special attention should be paid to the banks' compliance with the requirements set forth in this Regulation. **Accordingly, the supervisory examination program for each bank should include, among other issues, such issues as:**

- a) how the bank manages the internationally recognized 9 (nine) main risks (credit, market (interest rate, stock, currency, loan positions), liquidity, legal, reputation, strategic, compliance, operational risks), as well as, in our opinion, the remaining 8 (eight) risks (country, regional, sectoral, customer, business, payment, project, collateral positions) and determines the degree of risk;

- b) What tangible (capital, liquidity) and intangible (risk quality and control systems) resources does the bank have to manage these risks?

- c) Whether the amount of resources identified is sufficient to balance the risks.

The auditors should determine that the bank's approach to risk management, including its subsidiaries, is adequate for the conduct of its business and that it has implemented a risk discipline in the process of managing the risks inherent in its business.

The auditors should require that banks have a sound and effective system to identify, manage and control the risks inherent in the bank. They should conduct an independent assessment of the bank's strategies, policies, procedures and practices related to the issuance of credit and ongoing portfolio management, the conduct of foreign exchange operations, liquidity management and, given that banking activities are currently mainly defined by credit and foreign exchange operations, special attention should be paid during the on-site inspection to the management of risks related to these activities.

The examiner should assess on-site the identification, measurement, management and control of individual credit risk. The objective should include an assessment of any measurement tools used by the bank (such as internal risk ratings and credit models). In addition, they should determine that the management effectively manages the credit risk process and risk positions, in accordance with appropriate policies. Supervisors should use a number of methods for analysis to assess the quality of the credit risk system. Many elements of such an assessment include supervisors' determination that the bank uses "sound" asset valuation procedures.

Examiners should determine whether the bank's management recognizes problem loans at an early stage and takes appropriate measures. They should monitor trends in the credit portfolio and discuss with the executive branch in the event of a deterioration in market conditions. Supervisors should assess whether the bank's capital, together with unsecured reserves, is adequate for the level of credit risk that is identified and characteristic of the bank's activities.

When reviewing the adequacy of the credit risk management process, supervisors should determine whether the process is effective in managing risk:

- a) at the individual business or legal entity level;
- b) across a broad range of businesses and branches and on a consolidated basis.

After assessing the credit risk management process, supervisors should work with management to address any difficulties, address any increased concentrations of non-performing loans in the system, and establish additional provisions.

Supervisors should consider the prudential limits (e.g., large exposure limits) that apply to all banks. Regardless of the quality of the credit risk management process, such limits should include a limited exposure to individual borrowers and groups of related counterparties. Particular attention should be paid to the disbursement of loans to counterparties that are “related” to the banks or to each other.

If the examination determines that the bank's risk management is inadequate or that the bank's specific risk profile poses a problem for the bank, the National Bank of Georgia must exercise intensive special supervision.

This module discussed the issue of risk management and the specific impact it has on the life of an accounting firm. This module provided you with a framework for identifying, assessing, and responding to risks in your firm. It also discussed ethical issues that you should be aware of and safeguards that you should implement in your firm to respond to ethical threats. This module then discussed quality control processes and their important role in managing the firm's risks. The module also covered business continuity planning and discussed strategies for dealing with the death or incapacity of a practitioner. The module concluded with a discussion of firm liabilities and insurance, which discussed the types of insurance that are likely to be most

appropriate for practitioners. Practitioners are encouraged to be attentive and vigilant to all areas of risk within the firm and to seek ways to reduce or eliminate risks within the firm.

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